

Artificial intelligence-enhanced DTC command methods used for a four-wheel-drive system

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Apr 4, 2023

Revised Jun 9, 2023

Accepted Jun 25, 2023

Keywords:

Artificial intelligence

Direct torque control

Electric vehicle

Induction motor

Variable master slave control

ABSTRACT

This paper presents an artificial intelligence direct torque control (DTC) method for an electric vehicle (EV) drive system. The architecture of the proposed electric vehicle is that of four wheels each with an induction motor (IM). A comparative study of the different torque and speed controllers proposed in this paper is made. An electronic differential is used to control the speed of each wheel as well as a variable master-slave control (VMSC) for the management of the magnetic quantities because the motors on the same side are fed by the same converter. This study allows highlights the performance of the propulsion system in terms of dynamics and safety of the vehicle and better stability. The different controllers are implemented by the MATLAB/Simulink software and the simulation results obtained show better flexibility in the control of the vehicle. It is worth noting that direct torque control with fuzzy logic (DTFC) performs better than DTC associated with neural networks in terms of a time reduction increase of 1.47%, an overshoot of less than 5.33, and a static steady-state error close to zero.

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1. INTRODUCTION

There is no doubt that the preservation of the environment is a necessity given almost irreversible harmful climatic changes caused, among other things, by pollution due to the emission of greenhouse gases [1], [2]. Among the currently recommended solutions, the development of the electric vehicle (EV) is found. It must progressively replace the internal combustion engine vehicle. The related research and development programs are being implemented by the States (USA, China, India) [3] and the major automobile industries. The current automotive market has three variants [3], internal combustion vehicles, hybrid vehicles, and electric vehicles. The motive power of the EV is based on the electric actuator that provides its drive. The choice of the propulsion machine and its control strategy play a key role from a technical and economic point of view (ease of manufacture of equipment, cost reduction, reduction of torque and flow oscillations, solidity

in the face of road constraints) [4]. Induction motors are chosen as propulsion motors because of their higher efficiency, and low maintenance [4], [5]. These motors can only work optimally if they are driven by a proper control strategy such as direct torque control (DTC) [6].

EVs are gaining popularity due to their quiet, smooth, and emission-free operation, as well as their safety benefits, portable charging system, and improved fuel economy [7]. However, these vehicles have challenges such as excessive charging time and low energy density, which provide possible research areas for their improvement. These limitations can be overcome by implementing an effective control strategy. At this level, in modern research, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) has gained importance due to the need to select the most appropriate parameters, allowing the most efficient results [8], [9].

Thus in [10], a review of several direct torque control (DTC) schemes associated with fuzzy logic (FL), artificial neural networks (ANN), sliding mode control (CMG), and genetic algorithms (GA) were presented to improve the performance of an induction motor (IM). A comparison was made between these control systems in terms of algorithm complexity, parameter sensitivity, ripple reduction, switching loss, and speed tracking. The authors concluded that it was very difficult to choose an appropriate control scheme because it depended on the application, accuracy, hardware availability, reliability, and system cost. An ANN-based DTC scheme was introduced for an electric vehicle powered by a fuel cell [11]. This scheme used the flux of the stator as a control variable and the flux level was adjusted according to the torque demand of the EV to achieve high drive performance. In this paper, the authors examined the performance of an IM drive for EV propulsion without considering the actual vehicle dynamics (road load), range, and fuel economy.

Thus in [12], an improved direct instantaneous torque control (DITC) based on adaptive terminal sliding mode control (ATSMC) was proposed. This is a new DTC technique for motors. A DTC scheme based on a stator flux optimization algorithm to increase the range of an electric vehicle in terms of driving a 3 kW induction motor at full load is tested by considering the effect of core losses and leakage inductance as explain in [13]. Araria *et al.* [14] presented a DTC scheme for a battery and fuel cell-powered front-wheel-drive EV with an ANN speed PI controller allows for accurate reference speed tracking compared to traditional PI controllers using standard driving cycles such as the US environmental protection agency (EPA) and the new European driving cycle (NCCE). A comparative study between ANN and GA is done on an EV propulsion system to examine the torque setting, EV behavior in terms of range, speed, and fuel efficiency as elaborated in [7]. An evaluation of the percentage of charge rate and the energy consumption are made under various road conditions.

This study proposes to evaluate two direct torque control (DTC) methods combined with artificial intelligence for a four-wheel-drive system of an electric vehicle. A comparison is made between fuzzy logic (FL) and artificial neural network (ANN) tuning. Both algorithms are used to adjust the error of the electromagnetic torque and magnetic flux to reduce the magnitude of their ripples. The proposed propulsion system was tested on the standard worldwide harmonized light vehicles test procedure (WLTP) driving cycle and performance parameters such as range and fuel efficiency were evaluated. The responses of the two intelligent algorithms are observed in terms of algorithm complexity, torque and flow ripple, control efficiency, improved flexibility, speed tracking, and ease of implementation. The performance obtained by the simulations indicates their adaptability to the use of such a propulsion system.

2. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION AND MODELLING

2.1. EV dynamics

The architecture of the EV developed in this paper is a twin-engine EV as shown in Figure 1. It contains key components of the conventional EV. Dynamics of vehicle are described by yaw rate, and speed both longitudinal and lateral as (1)-(3) [15], [16]:

$$v_x = v_y r + \frac{F_{t1} + F_{t2} + F_{t3} + F_{t4} - F_{tot}}{M_v} + \frac{C_f \delta}{M_v} \left(\frac{v_y + r l_r}{v_x} - \delta \right) \quad (1)$$

$$v_y = \left(-\frac{C_r + C_f}{M_v v_x} \right) v_y + \left(\frac{C_r l_r + C_f l_f}{M_v v_x} - v_x \right) r + \frac{C_f}{M_v} \delta \quad (2)$$

$$r = \left(\frac{C_r l_r - C_f l_f}{J_v v_x} \right) v_y - \left(\frac{C_r l_r^2 - C_f l_f^2}{J_v v_x} \right) r + \frac{C_f l_f}{J_v} \delta + \frac{d}{J_v} (F_{t1} + F_{t2} - F_{t3} - F_{t4}) \quad (3)$$

When analyzing Figure 2 presented, different forces applied to the vehicle are mentioned for a better understanding. Then, in (4) indicating the EV resistance opposes to any movement can be easily carried out. Following forces, the tire rolling resistance F_{rr} , aerodynamic resistance in drag F_{wind} , levelling resistance F_g

and acceleration resistance F_l are needed for a calculation of the required total force all these resistances are discussed detailly in [17]–[19].

$$F_t = F_{rr} + F_{wind} + F_g + F_l \quad (4)$$

Where:

$$F_{rr} = gMv C_{rr} \cos\alpha \quad (5)$$

$$F_{wind} = 0,5\rho S_f C_{px}(V_h - V_{air})^2 \quad (6)$$

$$F_g = gM_v \sin\alpha \quad (7)$$

$$F_l = \gamma M_v \quad (8)$$

The longitudinal forces of four-wheel motors can be calculated using as (9) [20].

$$F_{ti} = \frac{\delta M_v}{4} \mu_i \cos(\alpha_p), i \in [1, \dots, 4] \quad (9)$$

The model of drive system can be described as (10) and (11) [20],

$$T_{ri} = F_{ti} R_\omega - N_f d_z, i \in [1, 3] \quad (10)$$

$$T_{ri} = F_{ti} R_\omega - N_r d_z, i \in [2, 4] \quad (11)$$

where T_{ri} is the resistive couple; N_f, N_r , are normal front and rear forces calculated using as (12) and (13) [20]:

$$N_f = \frac{gM_v}{2} \left(\frac{l_r}{L} - \frac{h_{cg}}{L_g} * \frac{dv_{cg}}{dt} \alpha_p - \frac{h_{cg}}{L} \alpha_p \right) \quad (12)$$

$$N_r = \frac{gM_v}{2} \left(\frac{l_r}{L} + \frac{h_{cg}}{L_g} * \frac{dv_{cg}}{dt} \alpha_p + \frac{h_{cg}}{L} \alpha_p \right) \quad (13)$$

with a linear tire model, front and rear cornering forces can be expressed as the product of the cornering stiffness. (C_f, C_r) and sideslip angle (α_f, α_r) [20].

$$F_{yf} = -C_f \alpha_f \quad (14)$$

$$F_{yr} = -C_r \alpha_r \quad (15)$$

Sideslip angles of the wheels are expressed using the side length and angular speeds, as well as the steering angle δ . The explicit expressions of sideslip angles for front and rear axles are represented by (16) and (17) [20].

$$\alpha_f = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{v_y + l_{fr}}{v_x} \right) - \delta \quad (16)$$

$$\alpha_r = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{v_y - l_{rr}}{v_x} \right) \quad (17)$$

The longitudinal slip needs to be determined for all four wheels as (18):

$$\lambda_i = \frac{R_\omega \omega_i - v_{ti}}{\max(R_\omega \omega_i - v_{ti})}, i \in [1, \dots, 4] \quad (18)$$

where: $i = 1, 2, 3$ and 4 correspond to front left, front right, rear left and rear right ($=lf, fr, rl, rr$) wheels, respectively; R_ω is the radius of wheel; ω_i is the angular speed of motor in the wheel, and V is the linear speed at which the contact zone moves on the ground. Inter relationships between slip ratio λ and the traction coefficient μ can be described by various formulas. In this study, the widely adopted magic formula [21], [22], is applied to describe relationship between sliding and tensile forces in order to build a vehicle model in which following simulations are indicated by (19) [23], [24].

$$\mu = C_1 \left[\sin \left(C_2 \tan^{-1} \left(C_3 \lambda - C_4 (C_3 \lambda - \tan^{-1}(C_3 \lambda)) \right) \right) \right] \quad (19)$$

The sets of coefficients of C1, C2, C3 and C4 are defined in [25], [26]

Figure 1. Architecture of the EV under investigation

Figure 2. Forces on the vehicle [19]

2.2. Modeling of the electronic differential (ED)

The ED allows the management of the driving wheel speeds of the EV. On a straight path, it maintains the two speeds of the driving wheels at the same value. And for a curvilinear trajectory, depending on whether we are going left or right, it allows the speed of the wheel at the outside position of the curve to be greater. This prevents the tires from losing traction [4]. Figure 3 shows a sketch of an electronic differential used in EV modeling. The notations L_w , d_w and δ represent the wheelbase, the distance between driving wheels and the steering angle, respectively. The speeds ω_R^* and ω_L^* are the drive speeds of right and left motors. So when: $\delta > 0 \rightarrow$ Turn right, $\delta = 0 \rightarrow$ Straight ahead, and $\delta < 0 \rightarrow$ Turn left

It is possible to determine the reference speeds in relation to the driver's requirements. When vehicle arrives at the start of a path, the driver applies a steering angle on its wheel [21], [27]. The ED acts instantly on both motors, reducing the speed of the wheel drive located at the inside position of the curve, thus increasing the speed of the driving wheel outside the curve. The angular speeds of the driving wheels are given by the relations:

$$\omega_R^* = \left(\frac{V_h}{R_\omega} - \frac{\Delta\omega}{2} \right) \tag{20}$$

$$\omega_L^* = \left(\frac{V_h}{R_\omega} + \frac{\Delta\omega}{2} \right) \tag{21}$$

The difference between the angular speeds of the driving wheels can be expressed by (22) [8], [28]:

$$\Delta\omega = \frac{d_w \tan(\delta)}{L_w} \cdot \frac{V_h}{R_\omega} \tag{22}$$

with $L_w = L_f + L_r$

Figure 3. Structure of the electronic differential [4], [27]

2.3. Variable master slave control (VMSC)

This is a switchable master-slave control strategy. In this system, it makes it possible to regulate the stator flux of machines placed in parallel. This is because the power to these machines is provided by a single converter, and it may happen that these machines do not undergo the same loads. This implies that the functioning of some can hamper that of others (for example, the magnetic circuit of one machine can become saturated without that of the other). To avoid this, a means must be found so that voltage vectors delivered by the converter supply each machine equitably by enabling it to develop speeds and torques which are respectively required of them. In this case, it is a matter of regulating the stator flux of one machine at a time. This machine will be called master and thus makes the other a slave. While the stator flux of the master machine is controlled, that of the slave machine evolves naturally without respecting the set point so as to avoid saturation. The master machine is the one with the lowest torque. We, therefore, observe that when the torque of a machine increases, its stator flux decreases and vice versa.

3. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE BASED DTC DEVELOPMENT

3.1. Direct torque control by artificial neural networks (DTNC)

The DTNC control for multi-machine systems is shown in the Figure 4. The inputs that provide the network are: $e_{Tem1}; e_{Tem2}$ (error between the torques developed by the motors and the corresponding references); e_ϕ (error between the modulus of the stator flux and the fixed reference) and θ_s (position of the stator flux vector in the complex plane (α, β)). And the outputs are the pulses Sa; Sb; Sc necessary to drive the converter allowing to feed the motors adequately. During the training of the network with the data provided by the simulation of the conventional DTC control, when data is presented at the input of the network, the output is obtained by a calculation propagated from the input layer to the output layer. The calculation of the quadratic sum of the errors is obtained by (23):

$$E(k) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (d_i(k) - y_i(k))^2 \tag{23}$$

with: d_i the desired output; y_i the computed output; k the number of iterations and N the amount of data in the training database. And so, according to the method of retro propagation of the error, the error is propagated from the output to the inputs causing a modification of the synaptic coefficients of the network according to as (24):

$$w_{ji}(k + 1) = w_{ji}(k) - \eta \frac{\partial E(k)}{\partial w_{ji}(k)} \tag{24}$$

with: w_{ji} the weight of the connection between the j-th neuron and the i-th neuron of the previous layer and η the learning constant. The network studies have the following characteristics:

- 4 layers, including 2 hidden layers each composed of 10 neurons. The input and output layers are composed of 3 neurons each.

- The activation functions used are linear (purelin) for the input and output layers and sigmoid (logsig) for the hidden layers.
- This is supervised learning, and the chosen learning algorithm is the backpropagation of error.
- The chosen optimization method is the Levenberg-Marquardt method for its speed and convergence.

Figure 4. Neural controller structure for multi-machine system

3.2. Direct torque control with fuzzy logic (DTFC)

The second technique proposed in this article is the DTC associated with fuzzy logic. The block diagram of this command (DTFC) for a multi-machine system is shown in Figure 1 above. The fuzzy regulator includes 4 inputs which are:

- e_φ : Difference between the reference stator flux and the estimated stator flux.
- $e_{T_{em1}}$: Difference between the reference torque and the electromagnetic torque of motor 1.
- $e_{T_{em2}}$: Difference between the reference torque and the electromagnetic torque of motor 2.
- θ_s : Position du vecteur de flux statorique.

The stake around the control for multi-machine systems with one converter is to ensure the optimal functioning of the actuators in parallel. Indeed, it must be ensured that the converter provides an adequate voltage vector to meet the demands of the machines. Thus, just like the conventional DTC command applied to this type of system, the DTFC command comprises in its structure a control loop as shown Figure 5 of an electromagnetic torque regulation based on a Mamdani type fuzzy regulator.

Thus, it includes two inputs: $e_{T_{em1}} = T_{emRef1} - T_{em1}^*$ for motor 1 and $e_{T_{em2}} = T_{emRef2} - T_{em2}^*$ for motor 2 and an exit $e_{T_{em}}$. The universe of discourses for each set is represented is being as: For e_φ we have: N (negative) and P (positive); and For $e_{T_{em1}}$, $e_{T_{em2}}$ we have: N (negative), Z (zero), and P (positive).

Trapezoidal and triangular membership functions were chosen. The torque error entry is made up of three fuzzy sets: N (negative), Z (zero) and P (positive) as shown in Figure 6 as shown in. This fuzzy regulator is governed by all the rules set out as shown in Table 1.

Figure 5. Structure of a fuzzy regulator for a multi-machine system

Figure 6. Membership function of torque error

Table 1. Basis of adopted rules

$e_{T_{em2}}$	$e_{T_{em1}}$		
	P	Z	N
P	P	P	Z
Z	P	Z	N
N	N	N	N

The output obtained will be used for the selection of the adequate voltage vector by another fuzzy regulator with as other inputs: i) The stator flux error; and ii) The position of the stator flux vector θ_s . The position of the stator flux vector is subdivided into six sectors. And for the outputs, the pulse signals used for the selection of the voltage vectors by the inverter are S_a , S_b , and S_c [20]. Thus, the rules obtained for the new method proposed can be deduced from the principle previously illustrated in the Table 1.

4. SIMULATION AND RESULT ANALYSIS

The simulation parameters used in this paper were chosen after an investigation in the literature. They come from the papers of [28], [29] with prototyping but also the papers [20], [27]. Table 2 gives the information of the path traveled by the vehicle. The vehicle leaves the stop state to reach the speed of 70 km/h at $t = 2s$. The driver maintains this speed until $t = 4s$. Between $t = 4s$ and $t = 9.5s$ the vehicle negotiates a right turn with a steering command of 7° is shown in Figure 7 and a speed of 50 km/h. Back on a straight line between $t = 9.5s$ and $t = 12s$ the vehicle is driving at 70 km/h. Left turn with a stabilized speed of 50 km/h between $t = 12s$ and $t=17.5s$. Then the Vehicle faces a slope of 10% until $t = 19s$ maintaining a speed of 40 km/h, then returns to a straight road for the rest of the trip at a speed of 50 km/h as shown in Figure 8. Thus, the chosen speed profile allows the vehicle to cover a distance of 290 m in the 20s as shown in Figure 9. Figure 10 allows us to appreciate the action of the electronic differential during the turns, the engines of the right side slower when the turn is on the right contrary to the engines of the left and vice versa. This is explained by the fact that the wheels on the inside of the curve support a significant weight of the vehicle moving towards the inside.

During the start [0s; 2s], the 04 motors that compose the system develop a very important torque to allow the vehicle to overcome the inertia and reach the speed wanted by the driver. During the turns [4s; 9.5s] and [12s; 17.5s], the torques of the motors located inside the turn increase to allow the wheels to keep the desired speed while supporting the weight of the vehicle which moves on their side, the motors located on the opposite side are driven which explains that the developed torques are of negative sign as shown in Figure 11. For conventional direct torque control, oscillations are significant and go beyond the set hysteresis range [-0.5N.m; 0.5N.m]. Figures 11(a) and 11(b) illustrate the contribution of artificial intelligence control techniques in reducing these oscillations, with DTFC offering the best result.

Table 2. Chronology of the journey made by the EV

Phases	Time (s)	Road information	Vehicle speed (Km/h)	Phases	Time (s)	Road information	Vehicle speed (Km/h)
01	0s <t< 2s	Starting the vehicle	70	05	12s<t<17.5s	Left turn	50
02	2s <t< 4s	Flat and straight road	70	06	17.5s <t<19s	10% slope	40
03	4s <t< 9.5s	Right turn	50	07	19s<t<20s	Flat and straight road	50
04	9.5s <t< 12s	Flat and straight road	70				

Figure 7. Steering angle variation

Figure 8. Speed profile

Figure 9. Distance traveled

Figure 10. Angular velocity references

Figure 11. Electromagnetic torque (a) DTFC and (b) DTNC

Motor speed response is better for DTFC control than for the other two strategies, as shown in Figure 12. Figure 12(a) shows the evolution of the speed curves derived from artificial intelligence and conventional vehicle control. Figure 12(b) shows the system's performance in terms of response. Table 3 shows some performance values.

Overall, the direct torque control strategy ensures good engine and vehicle control. Moreover, the results show the compatibility of this control for an application to multi-machines/mono converter systems,

which added to an energy-saving. Figures 13 and 14 shows the energy consumed by the vehicle for each type of control strategy proposed. In the two figures (Figures 13 and 14), we can see that the classical DTC consumes more energy than the DTNC and the DTFC.

Figure 12. Right front motor angular speed (a) angular speed and (b) zoom speed

Table 3. Dynamic parameters of the speed response for each motor

Dynamic Parameters	Rising Time (Sec)			Overshoot (%)			Speed Error (%)		
	PI	FL	ANN	PI	FL	ANN	PI	FL	ANN
	0.044	0.0209	0.0356	7.27	1.56	6.89	0.07	0.02	0.07

Figure 13. Electrical energy consumed by the vehicle

Figure 14. Zoom of the electrical energy consumed by the vehicle

To validate this model of a 4WD, 2-converter vehicle, goes through a confrontation with the WLTP driving cycle, the results of which are shown in Figure 15. This figure shows the speed of each engine of the vehicle. These speeds follow faithfully the setpoint imposed by the WLTP cycle. The proposed control system shows its robustness to the different constraints of the cycle. This ensures good stability of vehicle stability.

Figure 15. Speed profile with WLTP

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, two methods of controlling multi-machine systems for electric vehicle propulsion are proposed. The results obtained show that direct torque control combined with fuzzy logic and artificial neural networks, compared with conventional control, delivers high performance in terms of speed, precision, robustness and perfect setpoint tracking despite the strong disturbances imposed by road constraints. The vehicle speed results obtained during the simulations enable a quantitative assessment of the performance of the proposed control strategies. With regard to the results and analyses previously carried out within the strict framework of the hypotheses considered (hysteresis limit range.), it is clear that the DTFC control technique presents better results (response time, static error.) than conventional DTC and DTNC. On the other hand, it can be seen that energy dissipation is a crucial factor in the quality-price ratio of an EV, as it is linked to electricity storage and therefore to battery life (charge and discharge cycle). In addition, consideration of the variation in the number of rules in DTFC and DTNC may be a future line of research to make a definitive statement concerning the comparison between these two techniques in EV modeling. All in all, the use of a twin-engine system with a single converter enables the electric vehicle to save energy. This is observed when using the WLTP driving cycle.

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